

Study of azo ester mesogenic homologous series : 2-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthyl-1-azo-4''-methyl benzenes

H. R. Prajapati^{a*} and A. V. Doshi^b

^aChemistry Department, C. U. Shah Science College, Ahmedabad-380 014, Gujarat, India

E-mail : drhrprajapati@yahoo.co.in

^bChemistry Department, Matushri Virbaima Mahila Science and Home Science, College, Rajkot-360 007, Gujarat, India

Manuscript received 6 November 2008, accepted 15 January 2009

Abstract : Mesogenic homologous series : 2-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthyl-1-azo-4''-methyl benzenes is synthesized to understand the effects of structural variation on mesogenic characteristics. All the members of the homologous series exhibit enantiotropic nematic mesophase with threaded type of textures. Smectic mesophase does not occur in any homologue of the series even in the monotropic condition. Well-known odd-even effect is observed in the nematic isotropic transition curve. Thermal stabilities and liquid crystalline properties are compared with other structurally identical homologous series. Melting and transition temperatures are determined by hot stage polarizing microscope. Analytical data support the structures of molecules.

Keywords : Azomesogens, smectic, nematic, mesomorphism.

Introduction

The mesomorphic behaviour of an organic compound is sensitive to its molecular architecture. A slight change in the molecular geometry brings about considerable change in its mesomorphic properties. Homologous series¹ with -COO- and -N=N- central bridges have been synthesized. Present work is planned to understand the relation between mesomorphic properties and structural variation of the molecule.

Experimental

Homologues of the titled homologous series were synthesized as under :

- (i) Synthesis of 4-*n*-alkoxy benzoic acids from 4-hydroxy benzoic acid carried out by established known method²⁻⁴.
- (ii) Synthesis of 2-hydroxy naphthyl-1-azo-4'-methyl benzene was carried out by treating 4-methyl aniline and 2-naphthol by the usual method⁵⁻⁷. The azodye formed was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized in glacial acetic acid for several times. The yield is about 68.0%; m.p. 129.0 °C.
- (iii) Azoester were prepared by the treatment of cor-

responding acid chloride⁶ with azodye reported in (ii).

Analytical data supports the structure of the homologues. The melting points and transition temperatures were determined by Leitz Laborlux Polarizing Microscope with heating state. Analytical data and transition temperatures are recorded in Tables 1(a), 1(b) and 2 respectively.

Table 1(a). Elemental analysis for 2-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthyl-1-azo-4''-methyl benzenes

Sr. no.	R = <i>n</i> -Alkyl chain	Nitrogen (%)	
		Calcd.	Obsd.
1.	Methyl	7.07	6.99
2.	Ethyl	6.83	6.98
3.	Propyl	6.60	6.43
4.	Butyl	6.39	6.26
5.	Pentyl	6.19	5.99
6.	Hexyl	6.00	5.98
7.	Heptyl	5.83	5.54
8.	Octyl	5.66	5.49
9.	Decyl	5.36	5.26
10.	Dodecyl	5.09	4.86
11.	Tetradecyl	4.84	4.75

Homologue	IR spectra (cm ⁻¹)
Decyl	1457, 2871, 2919 cm ⁻¹ → Alkyl group
	1168, 1207, 1733 cm ⁻¹ → -COO- group
	748 cm ⁻¹ → <i>ortho</i> Substituted benzene
	814 cm ⁻¹ → <i>para</i> Substituted benzene
Tetradecyl	1457, 2849, 2919 cm ⁻¹ → Alkyl group
	1207, 1683, 1733 cm ⁻¹ → -COO- group
	750 cm ⁻¹ → <i>ortho</i> Substituted benzene
	813 cm ⁻¹ → <i>para</i> Substituted benzene
	IR confirms the above structure
Homologue	NMR spectra in CDCl ₃ , δ ppm
Butyl	0.94 (3H, t, -CH ₃)
	1.25 (4H, m, -CH ₂)
	2.42 (<i>para</i> Subs. 3H, s, -CH ₃)
	4.03 (2H, t, -OCH ₂)
	6.9-8.59 (14H, m, Ar-H)
Pentyl	0.94 (3H, t, -CH ₃)
	1.42 (6H, m, -CH ₂)
	2.40 (<i>para</i> 3H, s, -CH ₃)
	4.02 (2H, t, -OCH ₂)
	6.9-7.9 (14H, m, Ar-H)

Table 2. Transition temperatures for 2-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthyl-1-azo-4''-methyl benzenes

No of carbon atoms in <i>n</i> -alkyl chain	Transition temp. (°C)		
	Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
1	-	119.0	151.0
2	-	102.0	143.0
3	-	120.0	148.0
4	-	94.0	125.0
5	-	90.0	120.0
6	-	85.0	115.0
7	-	90.0	112.0
8	-	92.0	113.0
10	-	100.0	130.0
12	-	95.0	118.0
14	-	115.0	125.0

Results and discussion

Homologues of the titled homologous series; viz. 2-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthyl-1-azo-4''-methyl benzenes are entirely nematogenic in nature because mesomorphism commences from very first member of the series in enantiotropic manner without showing up of any smectogenic character even in the monotropic condition. Transition temperatures are plotted against the number of

carbon atoms in *n*-alkyl chain of the left *n*-alkoxy group as tabulated in the Table 2. Smooth curves are drawn through the like or related points of transitions as shown in Fig. 1. Solid-mesomorphic transition curve shows overall falling tendency upto sixth homologue and then rises with zigzag manner upto fourteenth homologue. Thus solid nematic curve follows zigzag path of overall falling and rising manner. The odd-even effect is observed in the nematic-isotropic transition curve and merges into each other at the seventh member of the series with alternation of transition temperatures. The nematic phase has threaded type of texture as judged directly by visualizing the sample of the homologues in a field of view of the hot stage polarizing microscope.

The nematic-isotropic transition temperatures are between 112.0 °C and 151 °C with mesomorphic range varying from minimum of 10.0 °C at fourteenth homologue to a maximum of 41.0 °C at the second homologue of the series. Smectic mesophase is totally absent. The titled homologous series is considered as middle ordered melting type with short range mesomorphism. Liquid crystals of moderate chain lengths yield only nematogenic homologues^{8,9} and is well supported by present investigation.

Substitution of fused phenyl ring at the middle phenyl ring (i.e. naphthyl unit) balances intermolecular forces of attractions in such a manner that molecule resists layer formation. Thus entire homologous series of mesogens are nematogenic without exhibition of any smectic character even in the monotropic condition. Absence of smectic character is attributed to insufficient intermolecular forces of attractions to form sliding layered arrangement of molecules in the crystal structure. Appearance of odd-even effect and alternation of transition temperature is attributed to the linking of number of methylene units through oxygen atom as *n*-alkoxy group. This effect diminishes as series is ascended from and beyond sixth or seventh member of the series because longer *n*-alkyl chains bends and coils without any contribution to odd-even effect. Nematic-isotropic transition curve abnormally behaves from and beyond seventh members of the series with maximum abnormality at the tenth homologue.

The characteristics of present homologous series¹ is compared with structurally similar other homologous series [A] and [B]¹⁰ (Fig. 2) for their molecular characteristics and thermal stabilities which are shown in Table 3.

Fig. 1. 2-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthyl-1-azo-4''-methyl benzenes.

Table 3. Average thermal stabilities in °C

Series	Series (1)	Series (A)	Series (B)
Nematic-isotropic or vice versa	127.27 (C ₁ -C ₁₄)	240.0 (C ₁ -C ₈)	152.14 (C ₁ -C ₇)
Commencement of nematic phase	C ₁	C ₁	C ₁

Homologous series (1) consists of three phenyl rings, central -COO- and -N=N- bridges, left *n*-alkoxy terminal at *para* position and methyl group substituted at *para* position with right phenyl ring, and one fused phenyl ring with middle phenyl ring at *ortho* position (naphthyl unit) with respect to -N=N- bridge at middle part of the series (1).

Central -COO- and -N=N- bridges, left *n*-alkoxy termi-

nal at *para* position and right side methyl end group are common identical features for series (1), (A) and (B). They differ in middle part i.e. varied substituted units with middle phenyl ring as fused phenyl ring in case series (1) without any substitution (-H) of series (A) and laterally substituted methyl group in case of series (B) respectively.

Hence, the variation in mesomorphic characteristics and degree of mesomorphism is varied due to variation at the central ring.

The molecular structure of series (1) differs from series (A) and (B). The presence of additional fused phenyl ring in middle phenyl ring (naphthyl ring) at the central part and lateral methyl group at the *meta* position with respect to -N=N- bridge increases the breadth of the molecules of series (1) and (B).

Fig. 2

Thus broadening of molecules increases intermolecular distance resulting in decrease of intermolecular forces of attractions on one hand while on the other hand polarizability of the molecule increases resulting in the increase of intermolecular forces of attractions. Therefore average thermal stability depends upon the net resultant intermolecular forces of attractions out of two opposing effects. Results of average thermal stability of series (1) and (B) suggests that their thermal stabilities are lower than the average thermal stability of series (A) because molecular geometry of the molecule of series (A) is like without lateral substitution. Difference in the average thermal stability of series (1) and (B) is observed due to degree of intermolecular attractions caused by fused phenyl ring and methyl group linked at the middle phenyl ring.

Gray¹¹ viewed that increase in the breadth of the molecules reduces both nematic and smectic mesophase thermal stability. Thus Gray's view is supported by present

investigation. It seems that the naphthyl ring at *ortho* position and methyl group at *meta* position with respect to -N=N- bridge at the central part of series (1) and (B) not only increases the breadth of the molecules of series (1) and (B), but also increases the non coplanarity in the system due to steric interactions. Both these factors would eliminate the smectogenic property for title homologous series (1) under present investigation. Nematic-isotropic thermal stability of series (1) is the lowest as compared to homologous series (A) and (B). This is because of broadening of molecule as concluded by Gray¹¹.

Thus, from the above discussion, nematic group efficiency order derived on the basis of middle part of molecule for nematic-mesophase is as follows :

Group efficiency order :

Conclusions :

New mesogenic homologous series of naphthalene derivative was synthesized. The study indicates the naphthyl ring adversely affects the mesophase thermal stability and induces nematic character with elimination of smectic character. Lateral substitution decreases average thermal stability. Thus credibility to Gray's view¹¹ is raised by present investigation.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head and teaching staff of Applied Chemistry of Faculty of Technology and Engineering, M. S. University, Baroda for their valuable co-operation in the work. The authors are also thankful to CSMCRI, Bhavnagar for the analysis of samples.

References

1. N. H. Shah, R. A. Vora and N. D. Jadav, *Mol. Cryst. Liq. Cryst.*, 1991, **209**, 291.
2. A. I. Vogel, "Textbook of Organic Chemistry", Longman, Green and Co. Ltd., 1968, 1000.

3. G. N. Vyas and N. M. Shah, "Org. Syn. Cell.", Vol. IV (Revised edition of annual Volumes 30-39), John Wiley and Sons, Inc, New York, 1963, 836.
4. J. S. Dave and R. A. Vora, "Liquid Crystals and Ordered Fluids", eds. J. F. Jonson and R. S. Portern, Plenum Press, New York, 1970, **1**, 477.
5. U. C. Bhoya and A. V. Doshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 249.
6. A. V. Doshi and K. J. Ganatra, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Bangalore*, 1999, Vol. III, 563.
7. A. V. Doshi and B. C. Chauhan, *Acta Ciencia Indica*, 2003, **29C**, 107.
8. G. W. Gray, "Molecular Structure and the Properties of Liquid Crystals", Academic Press, London and New York, 1962.
9. U. C. Bhoya and A. V. Doshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 143.
10. A. V. Doshi and B. C. Chauhan, *Acta Ciencia Indica*, 2003, **21C**, 107.
11. G. W. Gray, "Molecular Structure and the Properties of Liquid Crystals", Academic Press, London and New York, 1962.